

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社内担当者 A

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2024/10/10

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

スルフォラファングルコシノレート (以下、SGS) の経口摂取による認知機能の維持・向上作用に関するメタアナリシス (以下、MA) を含むシステマティック・レビュー

This search strategy is

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

疾病に罹患していない成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合と比較して、認知機能を維持・向上するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P 疾病に罹患していない成人(妊産婦、妊娠を計画している者、および授乳婦を除く。)

I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取

C SGS を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合

O 認知機能を維持・改善

ランダム化並行群間比較試験(RCT-P)、ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(RCT-C)、準ランダム化並行群間比較試験

S (qRCT-P)、準ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(qRCT-C)、非ランダム化並行群間比較試験(nonRCT-P)、非ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(nonRCT-C)、非ランダム化比較試験

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

—

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

—

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

—

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

—

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 Sulphoraphane/TH or "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforaphan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or SFN/TA or 実生/MTH
#2 Glucoraphanin/TH or グルコラファニン/TA or Glucoraphanin/TA
#3 #1 or #2
#4 "Glucosinolates"/TH or "Isothiocyanates"/TH or "Glucosinolates"/TA or グルコシノレート/TA or グルコシノラート/TA or "Isothiocyanates"/TA or イソチオシアネート/TA or イソチアシアン酸類/TA or イソチオシアナート/TA
#5 SGS/TA or アブラナ科/TH
#6 #4 or #5
#7 #3 and #6
#8 #7 not ((CK=動物) not (CK=ヒト))
#9 (#8) and (PT=会議録除く)

Key articles:

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2024/10/24

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested

- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested

C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社内担当者 A

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2024/10/01

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS の経口摂取による認知機能の維持・向上作用に関するメタアナリシス MA を含む SR

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

MEDLINE

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

PubMed

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

疾病に罹患していない成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合と比較して、認知機能を維持・向上するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P 疾病に罹患していない成人(妊産婦、妊娠を計画している者、および授乳婦を除く。)

I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取

C SGS を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合

O 認知機能を維持・改善

ランダム化並行群間比較試験(RCT-P)、ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(RCT-C)、準ランダム化並行群間比較試験

S (qRCT-P)、準ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(qRCT-C)、非ランダム化並行群間比較試験(nonRCT-P)、非ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(nonRCT-C)、非ランダム化比較試験

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

—

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

—

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. [mandatory if the answer was YES]

—

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? [optional]

—

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. [mandatory]

#1 "sulforaphane glucosinolate"[ftw] OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate"[tiab:~2]

#2 "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"[Title/Abstract:~0] OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate"[Title/Abstract] OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"[Title/Abstract:~0] OR sulphoraphan*[TW] OR sulforaphan*[TW]
#3 "sulforaphane" [Supplementary Concept]
#4 #2 OR #3
#5 "Glucosinolates"[MeSH] OR Glucosinolate*[tw] OR SGS[tw]
#6 #4 AND #5
#7 "Sulfoxides"[Mesh] OR "Sulfoxides"[tw]
#8 "Isothiocyanates"[MeSH] OR Isothiocyanate*[tw]
#9 #7 AND #8
#10 glucoraphanin[nm] OR glucoraphanin[tw]
#11 #1 OR #6 OR #9 OR #10
#12 (clinical trial[pt] OR comparative study[pt] OR (control[tw] AND study[tw]) OR program[tw] OR epidemiologic studies[mh]) NOT ((animals[mh:noexp] NOT humans[mh:noexp]) OR comment[pt] OR editorial[pt] OR review[pt] OR meta analysis[pt] OR case report[tw] OR consensus[mh] OR guideline[pt] OR history[sh])
#13 #11 AND #12
#14 (randomized controlled trial [pt] OR controlled clinical trial [pt] OR randomized [tiab] OR placebo [tiab] OR clinical trials as topic [mesh:noexp] OR randomly [tiab] OR trial [ti]) NOT (animals [mh] NOT humans [mh])
#15 #11 AND #14
#16 #13 OR #15

Key articles:

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2024/10/07

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

研究デザインについて：

ご確認ありがとうございます。

RCT 以外の研究デザインに関して、ある程度拾えていれば OK でしたら

そのままでもいいかと思えます。

仰る通り、昨年の方が少し広めに拾っています。

プロトコル「方法」(p.3)に記載の研究デザインのうち non-RCT について、

去年は、検索フィルターを探してきて#12 で使用されていました。

今回プロトコル検索式#5 と比べると、以下が特に追加されていました。

clinical trial[pt]・・・RCT 以外の下位概念が今回含まれていません

comparative study[pt]・・・今回プロトコルに含まれておらず漏れます

epidemiologic studies[mh]・・・下位概念のうち以下 3 つは今回プロトコルに含まれます

- Case-Control Studies
- Cohort Studies
- Cross-Sectional Studies

上記の比較研究なども網羅した方がよい、ということでしたら、

今回プロトコルの#5 の箇所を、以下例のようにしてはいかがでしょうか。

(※#5 と、今年の#12 をマージした式です)

(clinical trial[pt] OR comparative study[pt] OR (control[tw] AND study[tw]) OR program[tw] OR epidemiologic studies[mh] OR "control groups"[MeSH Terms] OR ("case"[Title/Abstract] AND "control"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("case"[Title/Abstract] AND "comparison"[Title/Abstract]) OR "control group"[Title/Abstract] OR "cohort"[Title/Abstract] OR "longitudinal"[Title/Abstract] OR "prospective"[Title/Abstract] OR "retrospective"[Title/Abstract] OR "cross-sectional"[Title/Abstract] OR "transversal

stud**[Title/Abstract]) NOT (comment[pt] OR editorial[pt] OR review[pt] OR meta analysis[pt] OR case report[tw] OR consensus[mh]
OR guideline[pt] OR history[sh])

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社内担当者 A

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2024/10/10

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS の経口摂取による認知機能の維持・向上作用に関する MA を含む SR

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Wiley)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

疾病に罹患していない成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合と比較して、認知機能を維持・向上するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P 疾病に罹患していない成人(妊産婦、妊娠を計画している者、および授乳婦を除く。)

I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取

C SGS を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合

O 認知機能を維持・改善

ランダム化並行群間比較試験(RCT-P)、ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(RCT-C)、準ランダム化並行群間比較試験

S (qRCT-P)、準ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(qRCT-C)、非ランダム化並行群間比較試験(nonRCT-P)、非ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(nonRCT-C)、非ランダム化比較試験

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

—

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

—

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

—

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

—

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 *sulforaphane NEXT/6 glucosinolat*:ti,ab,kw in Trials*

#2 ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulphoraphan* OR sulforaphan*):ti,ab,kw in Trials
#3 MeSH descriptor: [Glucosinolates] explode all trees in Trials
#4 (Glucosinolate* OR SGS):ti,ab,kw in Trials
#5 #3 OR #4 in Trials
#6 #2 AND #5 in Trials
#7 MeSH descriptor: [Sulfoxides] explode all trees in Trials
#8 (Sulfoxides):ti,ab,kw in Trials
#9 #7 OR #8 in Trials
#10 MeSH descriptor: [Isothiocyanates] explode all trees in Trials
#11 (Isothiocyanate*):ti,ab,kw in Trials
#12 #10 OR #11 in Trials
#13 #9 AND #12 in Trials
#14 (glucoraphanin*):ti,ab,kw in Trials
#15 #1 OR #6 OR #13 OR #14 in Trials

Key articles:

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2024/10/24

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
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- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
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- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

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5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
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Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Sulforaphane-rich、Glucoraphanin-rich の件、コクランのみ対応すればよいように思います。

#2 : sulphoraphan*が入っており、-rich が拾えます。

※ただし、#5 と AND 検索しているため、#4 のキーワード検索にブロッコリーの語を加えてはどうかと思います。

そうしますと、拾えていなかった先日の 4 件も含まれてきます。

もし検索式の構成に違和感を感じられるようでしたら教えてください。

#14 : glucoraphanin*が入っており、-rich が拾えます。

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This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

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Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

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PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P 疾病に罹患していない成人(妊産婦、妊娠を計画している者、および授乳婦を除く。)

I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取

C SGS を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合

O 認知機能を維持・改善

ランダム化並行群間比較試験(RCT-P)、ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(RCT-C)、準ランダム化並行群間比較試験

S (qRCT-P)、準ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(qRCT-C)、非ランダム化並行群間比較試験(nonRCT-P)、非ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(nonRCT-C)、非ランダム化比較試験

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

—

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

—

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

—

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

—

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 *tw:("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")*

#2 (tw:("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin))
#3 tw:("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")

Key articles:

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2024/10/24

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社内担当者 A

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2024/10/10

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS の経口摂取による認知機能の維持・向上作用に関する MA を含むシステマティック・レビュー

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

疾病に罹患していない成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合と比較して、認知機能を維持・向上するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P 疾病に罹患していない成人(妊産婦、妊娠を計画している者、および授乳婦を除く。)

I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取

C SGS を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合

O 認知機能を維持・改善

ランダム化並行群間比較試験(RCT-P)、ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(RCT-C)、準ランダム化並行群間比較試験

S (qRCT-P)、準ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(qRCT-C)、非ランダム化並行群間比較試験(nonRCT-P)、非ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(nonRCT-C)、非ランダム化比較試験

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

—

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

—

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

—

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

—

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")

#2 "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin
#3 in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")
#4 in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")
#5 in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin)
#6 in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")

Key articles:

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2024/10/24

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社内担当者 A

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2024/10/10

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS の経口摂取による認知機能の維持・向上作用に関する MA を含む SR

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

疾病に罹患していない成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合と比較して、認知機能を維持・向上するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P 疾病に罹患していない成人(妊産婦、妊娠を計画している者、および授乳婦を除く。)

I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取

C SGS を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合

O 認知機能を維持・改善

ランダム化並行群間比較試験(RCT-P)、ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(RCT-C)、準ランダム化並行群間比較試験

S (qRCT-P)、準ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(qRCT-C)、非ランダム化並行群間比較試験(nonRCT-P)、非ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(nonRCT-C)、非ランダム化比較試験

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

—

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

—

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

—

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

—

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")

#2 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin) AND "Glucosinolates")
#3 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")
#4 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")
#5 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")
#6 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")

Key articles:

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2024/10/24

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社内担当者 A

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2024/10/10

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS の経口摂取による認知機能の維持・向上作用に関する MA を含む SR

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

疾病に罹患していない成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合と比較して、認知機能を維持・向上するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** 疾病に罹患していない成人(妊産婦、妊娠を計画している者、および授乳婦を除く。)
- I** SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C** SGS を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取もしくは何も介入を行わない場合
- O** 認知機能を維持・改善
- S** ランダム化並行群間比較試験(RCT-P)、ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(RCT-C)、準ランダム化並行群間比較試験(qRCT-P)、準ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(qRCT-C)、非ランダム化並行群間比較試験(nonRCT-P)、非ランダム化クロスオーバー試験(nonRCT-C)、非ランダム化比較試験

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

—

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

—

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. [mandatory if the answer was YES]

—

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? [optional]

—

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. [mandatory]

#1 検索： 目的1 スルフォラファングルコシノレート
 #2 検索： 目的1 sulforaphane glucosinolate

- #3 検索：目的1 Sulphoraphane
- #4 検索：目的1 スルフォラファン
- #5 検索：目的1 スルフォラフェン
- #6 検索：目的1 Glucoraphanin
- #7 検索：目的1 グルコラファニン
- #8 検索：目的1 ブロッコリスプラウト
- #9 検索：目的1 BS 抽出物
- #10 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード スルフォラファングルコシノレート
- #11 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード *sulforaphane glucosinolate*
- #12 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Sulphoraphane
- #13 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード スルフォラファン
- #14 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード スルフォラフェン
- #15 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Glucoraphanin
- #16 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード グルコラファニン
- #17 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ブロッコリスプラウト
- #18 フリーワード検索：検索キーワード BS 抽出物

Key articles:

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2024/10/24

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example: